

Influence of Service Quality on Tourists' Satisfaction When Coming To Hanoi

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Abstract:

The objective of this paper is to apply SERVQUAL's service quality model to evaluate factors affecting tourism service quality and the impact of tourism service quality on tourist satisfaction. Visiting at tourist destinations in Hanoi. The analysis results using SPSS 22 and Smart PLS 3.0 software show that all the hypotheses are supported.

Keywords: Service quality, tourist satisfaction, Hanoi, Vietnam

1. Introduction

Services play an increasingly important role in the economies of each nation. Having grasped such an important role, many experts in the world have focused on the field of service quality. However, most of the research focused on developing countries (Herbig & Genestre, 1996). Very few studies on service quality have been verified in the Asian market (Cui et al., 2003). In Vietnam, it can be said that Nguyen Dinh Tho and his colleagues are the pioneers of SERVQUAL's application (Parasuraman & ctg, 1988) in the field of service quality research. By this time, many studies on various service quality areas such as banks, supermarkets, hospitals, hotels, etc. have been completed, contributing to the development of the service quality scale in Vietnam and world. In the field of tourism services, there are many studies on restaurants and hotels in Vietnam, but there are few studies on the quality of tourism services and most of them just stop at the survey. Opinions of customers by descriptive statistics and few studies measuring and using a scale methodically and scientifically.

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Among the tourist sites in Vietnam, Hanoi City is home to favorable climatic conditions, natural landscapes and historical places. The number of international and domestic tourists coming to Hanoi has been increasing, however, in recent times, the tourism quality and infrastructure of the tourist areas have been degraded. In addition, asynchronous development strategies, fragmented tourism business have quickly destroyed the landscape, tourism environment and tourism image of Hanoi city. Tourism business is not only about attracting more visitors but also how to keep visitors, ensuring good service quality to meet their needs. Therefore, the tourist areas in Hanoi need to master the tastes and behaviors of tourists to give appropriate directions, improve the quality of service to please and attract visitors effectively. Those are the reasons for me to choose the quality of service, satisfaction and loyalty as my research orientation in tourist areas in Hanoi.

This study aims to explore and develop the service quality scale for tourist resorts, thereby to measure the service quality of tourist areas in Hanoi, and to consider the impact of regional service quality. travel to the satisfaction and loyalty of travelers.

The project uses SERVQUAL service quality scale (Parasuraman & ctg, 1988) and inherits from the service quality scale of entertainment area of Nguyen Dinh Tho (2003). The research is conducted through 2 main steps: Preliminary research and formal research. Preliminary studies are conducted through qualitative methods.

Hand-to-hand discussion technology is used and used to discover and supplement the service quality scale model along with customer satisfaction. The official study was carried out by the questionnaire survey in tourist areas in Hanoi, qualitative research to develop, calibrate the questionnaire and in-depth study of tourist suggestions in improving quality. travel. Quantitative research in the measurement, testing of scales, testing of research models.

This is one of the first studies using SERVQUAL application scale to measure service quality for Hanoi tourist areas. It can be a basis for further research in the service sector, especially in the field of tourism.

The study has made important contributions to the development of the service quality scale of tourist resorts in Hanoi, while also contributing to understanding the factors affecting satisfaction and satisfaction. Loyalty of tourists. However, this is just an inception study, more research is needed in areas such as hotels, restaurants, tours ... and also suggests that further studies can continue to be based on the limitations of the topic such as stratified sampling, additional interviews with foreign visitors, further research on the influence of qualitative variables and multi-group analysis.

2. Literature review

2.1. Service

Currently, there is much debate about the service concept. So far people have many concepts such as:

Philip Kotler defines: Services are all actions and results that one party can provide to the other and are essentially invisible and do not lead to ownership of something. Its products may or may not be associated with the physical product.

According to the German dictionary: Service is not performed workers relating to the production of goods.

According to the Chinese Dictionary of Market Economy: Services in the narrow sense are activities that do not produce material wealth, because those who put in labor provide intangible efficiency without tangible products ... broadly speaking, these are activities that bring living labor into the physical product to satisfy certain needs of others.

According to the dictionary of financial and economic terms: Services are services that contribute to meeting the needs of individuals or groups. In Economics: Services are understood to be similar to goods but immaterial. There are products that are tangible and products that are very service-oriented, but most of them are in the gap between products and services.

All service providers (producers) constitute the third sector of the economy. According to Party Congress documents, services include trade and services. The provisions of the WTO relating to services also include two agreements: the Agreement on Trade in Goods (GATT) and the Agreement on Trade in Services (GATS). Also according to the WTO, the service sector of the service sector is divided into 12 sectors: business services; telecommunication services; distribution service; education services; environmental services; Financial services; social services and travel; cultural and entertainment services; Service of transportation; construction services and construction engineers; other services

2.2. Service quality

Service quality is the extent to which a service meets its needs and needs

customer expectations (Lewis & Mitchell, 1990; Asubonteng et al., 1996; Wisniewski & Donnelly, 1996);

Edvardsson, Thomsson & Ovretveit (1994) think that service quality meets customer expectations and satisfies their needs;

Lehtinen & Lehtinen (1982) argue that service quality must be assessed on two dimensions, (1) the service

delivery process and (2) the outcome of the service;

Gronroos (1984) argued that service quality is the quality that customers perceive through the service they receive and that service quality is recommended in two areas, (1) technical quality and (2) functional quality. Technical quality refers to what is served and the functional quality speaks to how they are served;

However, Parasuraman & ctg (1985) is considered a pioneer in detailing service quality in detail, according to this researcher, service quality can be measured through measurement. the difference between the level of expectation and the true perceived value of a customer about that service. And the quality of service is assessed based on the year of difference or the gap.

2.3. SERVQUAL model

In 1988, Parasuraman et al al corrected and formed a new model with five components. That is the SERVQUAL model

Definition of factors in SERVQUAL:

Reliability: Demonstrated through the ability to perform services appropriately and on time the first time. Capability of serving employees to honor promises correctly.

Reponsiveness: Expressed through the wishes and readiness of employees to provide timely services to customers.

Service capacity (Assurance): Demonstrated through professional qualifications and service manner with customers.

Empathy: Show caring for each individual customer.

Tangibles: Including physical assets, pages device.

Many other researchers have also implemented the model of 5 components of service quality in many service sectors as well as many different markets. Assessment results show that service quality is not uniform among different service industries. Another issue raised is the importance of each component of service quality to customer satisfaction. Therefore, more research is needed in this area. And also according to Babakus and Boller (1992), it is necessary to have a specific service quality scale for each industry.

Currently, many researchers in Vietnam have applied SERVQUAL model of Parasuraman et al (1988) such as Nguyen Dinh Tho et al (2003) to apply measurement and develop this scale for service sector. entertainment of TP. Ho Chi Minh; Nguyen Thi Mai Trang (2006) researches on service quality, satisfaction, loyalty of supermarket customers in Ho Chi Minh City; Nguyen Thi Phuong Tram (2008) studied the quality of electronic banking services; Mai Thuy Ninh (2009) researches on service quality, satisfaction, loyalty of tourists about hotels in Nha Trang

2.3. Service quality and customer satisfaction

Once the income increases, people's lives are improved, the demand for quality consumption is increasing, the demands are increasing and customers are more and more difficult. Therefore, it is necessary to evaluate the quality of service to know what the customer's expectations are and according to researchers, businesses will have many advantages if their customers always have a high level of satisfaction. Because it increases the loyalty of customers to the brand, minimizes price sensitivity, significantly saves the costs of marketing, increases efficiency in advertising activities and improves get the image of the business. (Fornell, 1992)

There are different viewpoints on customer satisfaction (Oliver 1997). Bachelet (1995; 81) states that: "Customer satisfaction is the feedback of consumers, the comments about the characteristics of the product, service or the product itself. These reflections will show the different levels of customer satisfaction when they consume products and services. "Therefore, the author said that customer satisfaction is an emotional response of customers. with their experience with a product or service.

Usually service providers often assume that the quality of service is the level of customer satisfaction. However, many studies show that service quality and customer satisfaction are a general concept, expressing their satisfaction when consuming a service. Meanwhile, the quality of service only focuses on the specific

components of the service (Zeithaml & Bitner 2000).

Many researchers have established this relationship and show a relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction (eg Cronin & Taylor 1992; Spreng & Mackoy 1996). However, very few studies have focused on testing the level of interpretation of service quality components for customer satisfaction, particularly in specific service industries (Lassar et al. 2000).

3. Research method

Based on the above relevant studies and the research of Nguyen Dinh Tho (2003) on measuring the quality of outdoor recreation services in Ho Chi Minh City. HCM. The studies on satisfaction rating Tran Duc Long (2006), Mai Thuy Ninh (2009) ... and synthesized from the qualitative discussion results from experts. The research model is as follows:

Figure 1: Research model

The initial hypotheses:

- H 1: Reliability (TC) positively affects service quality
- H 2: Response (DU) positively affects service quality
- H 3: Service capacity (NL) positively affects service quality
- H 4: Empathy (DC) positively affects service quality
- H 5: Tangible equipment (HH) positively affects service quality
- H 6: Price (GC) positively affects service quality

H 7: Service quality positively affects customer satisfaction

Research sample

Selected by the convenient sampling method. Methods of data collection by questionnaire. The author directly interviewed and distributed questionnaires in tourist areas of Hanoi such as Van Mieu, lakeside, one-pillar pagodas, etc. As the place to welcome the largest number of visitors to Hanoi, the interview is conducted within a month from August 25 to September 25, 2019.

The collected data will be cleaned and processed by SPSS software 22. With SPSS software, perform data analysis through statistical descriptive tools, frequency tables, graphs, verifiers. Cronbach Alpha reliability of scales, EFA discovery factor analysis, confirmatory factor analysis (CFA), multiple regression analysis, estimation and testing of structural models (SEM) with Smart software PLS.

4. Research results

Cronbach's alpha method is used to eliminate inappropriate variables and limit spam variables during the study and evaluate the reliability of the scale by a coefficient through Cronbach's alpha coefficient. Variables with item-total correlation of less than 0.3 will be excluded. A scale with Cronbach's alpha coefficient of 0.6 or higher can be used in the case of a new concept under study (Nunnally, 1978; Peterson, 1994; Slater, 1995).

In the five components of the SERVQUAL scale above, we see that the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient is greater than 0.6. The trusted component has the smallest Alpha coefficient of 0.672 but is still greater than 0.6. The remaining components have good Alpha coefficients which are in the range of 0.7 - 0.9 and all correlation coefficients are greater than 0.3. For

See that we can use all these variables in the next analysis step

After evaluating the reliability of the scale using Cronbach's alpha coefficient, no variables were excluded. Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) is a technique used to shrink and summarize data. This method is useful for identifying the set of variables needed for a research problem and is used to find relationships between variables.

Previous studies often used the method of extracting principal components with varimax rotation. In this study, the Principal Axis Factoring method is used with Promax rotation for omnidirectional scale. According to Gerbing & Anderson (1988), Principal Axis Factoring method with Promax rotation (Oblique) will reflect the data structure more accurately than Principal Components extraction method with Varimax rotation (Orthogonal).

Nguyen Khanh Duy (2009) summarizes the research results and shows that the following factors need to be considered:

Interested in standards: | Factor Loading | Maximum of each Item > = 0.5

Interested in standards: At each Item, the difference | Factor Loading | biggest and | Factor Loading | any must be > = 0.3 (Jabnoun & Al-Tamimi, 2003)

Total variance extracted > = 50% (Gerbing & Anderson, 1988)

KMO > = 0.5, Bartlett test has statistical significance (Sig < 0.05)

Table 1

Construct Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Assurance	0.928	0.928	0.928	0.682
Customer satisfactio	0.920	0.925	0.920	0.698
Empathy	0.872	0.872	0.872	0.694
Price	0.872	0.872	0.872	0.694
Reliability	0.911	0.911	0.911	0.672
Responsiveness	0.898	0.898	0.898	0.638
Service quality	0.981	0.981	0.981	0.668
Tangibility	0.910	0.911	0.910	0.629

Table 2
Discriminant Validity
Fornell-Larcker Criterion

	Assurance	Customer satisfactio	Empathy	Price	Reliability	Responsiveness	Service quality	Tangibility
Assurance	0.826							
Customer satisfactio	0.461	0.836						
Empathy	0.194	0.131	0.833					
Price	0.232	0.196	0.038	0.833				
Reliability	0.188	0.250	0.267	0.289	0.820			
Responsiveness	0.026	0.170	0.022	0.182	0.009	0.799		
Service quality	0.021	0.157	0.016	0.161	0.012	0.038	0.818	
Tangibility	0.030	0.374	0.037	0.292	0.020	0.049	0.041	0.793

Figure 2. Research results

The results show that all the assumptions are accepted, all factors of reliability, responsiveness, service capacity, tangible facilities, and price issues have a positive and statistically significant impact. up to the 1% level of service quality (P_value = 0.000). Service quality has a strong impact on customer satisfaction with the impact level of 0.442 at the 1% significance level (P_value = 0.000). That means the tourism business in Hanoi area should enhance service quality to improve customer satisfaction.

Table 3 summarizes the results of the research hypotheses. All theories are supported

Table 3

Path Coefficients

Mean, STDEV, T-Values, P-Values

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Assurance -> Service quality	0.224	0.224	0.006	34.835	0.000
Empathy -> Service quality	0.115	0.115	0.005	21.224	0.000
Price -> Service quality	0.117	0.118	0.005	24.656	0.000
Reliability -> Service quality	0.186	0.185	0.004	45.476	0.000
Responsiveness -> Service quality	0.181	0.181	0.005	39.456	0.000
Service quality -> Customer satisfactio	0.442	0.445	0.041	10.703	0.000
Tangibility -> Service quality	0.217	0.217	0.005	39.749	0.000

5. Conclusion

The purpose of the study is to adjust and supplement the components of the service quality scale in tourist areas in Ho Chi Minh City. Da Lat. Besides, consider the influence of the components of the service quality scale on

the satisfaction and loyalty of visitors.

After analyzing and analyzing the model of research results on service quality scale including 5 factors (1) response - reliability; (2) tangible; (3) empathy;

(4) hygiene; (5) amusement services

The results of the regression analysis show that there are 5 factors that affect visitor satisfaction (1) tangible (2) responsiveness - trust (3) price (4) hygiene (5) spending little

SEM analysis results show that only 3 factors affect satisfaction

(1) tangible (2) responsive - reliable (3) price

And among these factors, the tangible factor has the strongest impact, which means that visitors are satisfied with the landscape and architecture in the tourist areas. And if there is an improvement in this factor, the satisfaction of visitors will increase, so the loyalty of the school also increases because the satisfaction has a strong influence on loyalty and if you do increase the satisfaction will increase the loyalty of visitors, the priority sequence when coming to this resort the next time will increase.

The research results contribute to the theoretical system of service quality in the field of tourism and contribute to the development of a strategy to improve service quality for the tourist areas in Ho Chi Minh City. Da Lat. Dalat has the advantage of a cool climate, beautiful natural landscapes of mountains, lakes, waterfalls and historical sites.

Moreover the tourist sites are not far from the city center, one day visitors can visit 5-7 locations.

Therefore, the tourist sites should focus on renovating and preserving natural landscapes, building artificial scenes and appropriate architectural works. There is a training strategy for tourism personnel and culture to create trust for visitors. Besides focusing on hygiene, price, service fees, especially building a rich entertainment area for each resort. Currently, the tourist resorts in Da Lat are quite poor in terms of recreation services, some tourist areas such as Dream Hill or Golden Valley do not have game services. For the youth group, when traveling, they not only admire the scenery but also enjoy participating in many new games that are also the majority of visitors' opinions in the survey to improve the quality of service resorts in Dalat.

Besides, the authorities should strictly manage the security issues at the tourist areas, should take measures for the situation of unclear prices and poor quality.

The study has made important contributions to the development of a service quality scale of tourist areas in Ho Chi Minh City. Dalat also contributes to the understanding of the factors that influence the satisfaction and loyalty of tourists. However, the topic also has some limitations as follows:

Firstly, the sampling of research samples is convenient (one of the non-probability sampling methods), so the representation is low, the ability to generalize to the crowd is not high. Further research should select a stratified sampling method (one of the probabilistic sampling methods) so that it will generalize and achieve statistical efficiency.

Secondly, the study was only conducted for the audience of Vietnamese tourists, it is necessary to do more research on foreign tourists, this is also a further research direction for future studies.

Thirdly, due to the research model of visitor satisfaction through the elements of service quality components, there has not been in-depth study of customer loyalty and the impact of qualitative and differential variables.

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